

THEORETICAL PREFERENCES OF COTTON CLEANING IN THE FINES CLEANING SECTION OF THE LKM-3 DEVICE

¹Kuliyev Tohir Mamaradjapovich, ²Jumaniyazov Kadam Jumaniyazovich, ³Lola
Anvarovna Djunayeva

¹doctor of technical sciences, professor, ²doctor of technical sciences, professor, ³PhD.
“Research Institute of Fiber Crops”

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of determining the contamination of cotton in small samples from small litter on the LKM-3 laboratory installation, depending on the number of slatted rows on a peg-slatted drum. According to the results of the experiments, it was determined that in the variant in which, on the peg drum, symmetrically located four peg rows are made slatted, the highest cleaning effect on fine litter is obtained.*

Keywords: *installation, pegs and slats, drum, cotton, weediness, variant, small rubbish, error.*

Аннотация. *В статье приведены результаты определения засоренности хлопка в малых пробах от мелкого сора на лабораторной установке ЛКМ-3 в зависимости от количества планчатых рядов на колково-планчатом барабане. По результатам опытов определена, что в варианте, на котором, на колковом барабане симметрично расположенные четыре колковые ряды выполнены планчатыми получается самый высокий очистительный эффект по мелкому сору.*

Ключевые слова: *установка, колково-планчатый, барабан, хлопок, засоренность, вариант, мелкий сор, погрешность.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada LKM-3 laboratoriya qurilmasidagi mayda axlatdan mayda namunalardagi g'ozaning qoziqli barabandagi shpal qatorlar soniga qarab ifloslanishini aniqlash natijalari keltirilgan. Tajribalar natijalariga ko'ra, qoziq barabani ustidagi nosimmetrik tarzda joylashtirilgan to'rt qator qoziqlar shpalli qilingan versiyada kichik qoldiqlarga eng yuqori tozalash effekti erishishi aniqlandi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *qurilma, qoziq-planka, baraban, paxta, ifloslik, variant, mayda ifloslik, xatolik.*

Introduction

The cotton complex occupies a central place in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The reforms implemented by the government in the cotton sector were the most important element of the country's systematic development and its transition to a market economy. The main products of the agro-industrial complex are raw cotton and its processed products; cotton seeds and its processed products; grain and its processed products; milk and dairy products and many others. The acceptance and technological processing of agro-industrial complex products involves technological processes such as drying, conditioning, humidification, pasteurization and storage. Among the parameters for monitoring and controlling technological processes, the most important parameter is contamination.

Raw cotton contamination data are essential for determining the quality and quantity of cotton at the time of raw cotton harvest and for monitoring the drying and cleaning of raw cotton in ginning mills.

At the same time, the actual state of affairs in this area indicates the presence of systemic problems and shortcomings that hinder the rapid development and modernization of production

processes, the introduction of advanced technologies and modern methods of corporate governance, as well as the rapid development of the industry as a whole [1].

Fast and reliable raw cotton data will enable breeders, farmers and ginners to identify and take the necessary measures in a timely manner to ensure the quality of cotton delivered at harvest time.

Research method: The stated problem is solved by the fact that the device for determining the contamination of raw cotton LKM-3, containing a hopper with a lid for loading the sample, the section of cleaning from small debris, consisting of a feed roller, two spike drums with grates and with an articulated automatically opening deck for the release of cotton from the section, the section of cleaning from large debris, consisting of a feeding paddle roller, saw drum with grate, lapping brush and removable paddle drum, located above it automatically opening flap to release the cleaned sample, regeneration section consisting of a saw drum, grate removable and guide paddle drums, tank for cleaned raw cotton and separated sap, guide of fine sap, the lower end of which is directed to the collector for weed impurities, installed on the platform of electronic scales under the grate of the regeneration section, which provides collection of fine and coarse sap in one place, the output of electronic scales is connected to the automatic control and calculation unit with software for controlling the measurement process, wherein in order to enhance the separation of fine sap in the sample during cleaning in the second in the course of the movement of the cotton, the electronic scales are connected to the automatic control and calculation unit with the software for controlling the measurement process, wherein in the second in the course of the movement of the cotton in the regeneration section. (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the improved device for determining the contamination of raw cotton LKM-3.

A) general view of the device;

Б) scheme of a stake-plate drum for cleaning from fine sap.

Cleaning of fine sap in the staking section is carried out with the help of staking drums with slats, in which in the second staking drum in the course of cotton feeding the height of blades is made at the level of stakes, which is 1/3 more than in the installation LKM-2, due to which it allows to raise the productivity of the air flow created by slats in 30%. This promotes the separation of fine dregs through the grate, which fall into the fine dregs guide, and from there into the general collection of fine and coarse dregs [2].

The improved laboratory unit (Fig. 1) contains a hopper for loading a sample of raw cotton 1, with a lid 2, mounted on a hinge, the section of cleaning from fine sap, containing a feed roller 3, two drums - stake 4 and stake-plank 5, with a grate 6 with an articulated fixed automatically opening deck 7, with the second in the course of feeding cotton in the stake-plank drum slats 28 have a height h_i equal to the height h of the stake 29 to strengthen the air flow, under the grate, at an angle of $\alpha = 58^\circ$

installed guide fine soror 8, on the back side of which in two sections installed two shock-shaking mechanisms 27, which affect the guide fine soror with a frequency of 30 strokes per minute alternately. Below the shaking section in the course of material supply is located section of cleaning from coarse debris, including the feeding paddle roller 9, lapping brush 10, grate 11, serrated drum 12, removable paddle drum 13 and located above it flap 14, a container for cleaned sample 15. The axes of the second in the course of the material supply of the peel drum 5 and serrated drum 12 of the cleaning section and the feed paddle roller 9 lie in the same plane, inclined at an angle of $c = 58^\circ$ to the horizontal, in this case they are installed with the possibility of interaction with each other, the direction of rotation of the peel drum 5 and serrated drum 12 coincide, and the feed paddle roller 9 has the opposite direction of rotation.

Below the serrated cleaning section is installed regeneration section, including a guide of coarse sap and fallen flyings 16, installed at an angle of $\gamma=45^\circ$ relative to the horizontal, serrated drum 17, lapping brush 18, grate 19 and removable paddle drum 20, and serrated drums of cleaning 12 and regeneration sections 17 are installed with the possibility of interaction one with another by means of removable paddle drum of regeneration section 20. The serrated drums and the removable paddle drums rotate in opposite directions. Under the grate of the regeneration section, a weed collector 21 is mounted on the platform of the electronic scales 22 on a plate 23 seated on a vibrating carrier 24. The output of electronic scales is connected to the automatic control unit 25 located on the front panel [3].

Figure 2. Installation of a stake and slat drum on the LKM-3

Developed working drawings, according to which manufactured stakes and slats drums for installation in the section of raw cotton cleaning from fine trash device LKM-3 (Fig. 2) on which symmetrically installed slat rows were performed - 2, 4 and 6, that is, three variants of stakes and slats drums were made.

Obtained results: of tests LKM-3 device with stake-plank drums to determine the efficiency of cleaning raw cotton from fine litter

Note:

- 1-variant, a stake-slat drum, on which, the slats are installed in two symmetrical rows;
- 2-variant, the same, on which the slats are set in four symmetrical rows;
- 3-version, the same, on which the slats are set in six symmetrical rows.

We take into account the actions of the distributed forces over the area of the bar

$$\vec{N} = \vec{Q} = \vec{q} \cdot AB$$

**Figure 3. Scheme of acting resistance forces during cotton cleaning
by a stake and-plank drum**

In the developed device LKM-3 on the second in the course of the staking drum is made staking-plate, so we will consider the distribution of the acting forces taking into account the introduced change. The scheme of acting forces is shown in Fig. 3.

The experiments were conducted using raw cotton of Buhoro 6 selection variety. Repetition of each variant of experiments was three times. The results of the experiments are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Effective and industrial cotton variety	Contamination by fine sod, determined on LKM-3, $Z_{LKMj}, \%$			Qual littering, by small debris, $Z_{rj}, \%$	Relative error, % (rel)		
	1st	2nd	3rd		1st	2nd	3rd
Buhoro 6, 1/1							
Buhoro 6, 1/1				5,9			
Buhoro 6, IV							

From the obtained data in Table 1 it follows that the use of a stakes and slats drum on the laboratory installation LKM-3 increases its cleaning effect on the chalk sap, respectively, the relative error of measurements to determine the contamination of cotton decreases. The conducted experiments have shown that the most effective effect is obtained in the second variant of experiments, with the use of a stake-plank drum, on which the slats are installed in four symmetrical rows.

Increase of slat rows up to staves reduces the cleaning effect on fine sod, explaining the excessive reduction of the number of cleaning stakes on the stake-slat drum.

Conclusions: Proceeding from the above described optimal variant of symmetrically installed slats on a stake and slat drum can be considered four rows, and the relative error of measurements is within the limits of permissible values established by the current standards.

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